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IL-16 expression is lost in the blood of humans with high CRP.

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We measured total transcription in the blood in humans with low CRP and in humans with high CRP to identify causative factors in cardiovascular disease mediated by inflammation. We describe here loss of IL-16 expression in humans with high CRP.